

THE HISTORY OF STATE IMAGE IN THE EXPERIENCE OF DEVELOPED COUNTRIES: USA

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Abstract

It is known that international cooperation has always been at the center of discussion of studies of two main liberal and realist directions. The predominance of the doctrine of liberalism in the XVII of XIX century was replaced by the theory of realism at the beginning of the XXI century. The study of the issue of international cooperation was formed as an independent scientific direction in the theory of international relations, which became popular in the 1950s. The study of this problem attracted the attention of scientists to such questions as the internal causes of cooperation, its place in the international environment that hinders or encourages development, causes and consequences of factors leading to cooperation, forms and types.

In this article is analyzed the history of the state image of developed countries using the example of the United States until the first quarter of the 20th century.

Key words: isolationism, globalism, pragmatism, liberalism, state image, ideology.

ИСТОРИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ИМИДЖА НА ОПЫТЕ РАЗВИТЫХ СТРАН: США

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Аннотация

Известно, что международное сотрудничество всегда было в центре обсуждения исследований двух основных либеральных и реалистических направлений. Господство доктрины либерализма в семидесятых годах XX века сменилось теорией реализма в начале XXI века. Исследование проблемы международного сотрудничества сформировалось как самостоятельное

научное направление в теории международных отношений, ставшее популярным в 1950-е годы. Исследование этой проблемы привлекло внимание ученых к таким вопросам, как внутренние причины сотрудничества, его место в международной среде, препятствующей или поощряющей развитие, причины и последствия факторов, приводящих к сотрудничеству, формы и виды.

В статье анализируется история государственного имиджа развитых стран на примере США до первой четверти XX века.

Ключевые слова: изоляционизм, глобализм, прагматизм, либерализм, государственный имидж, идеология.

Introduction. The United States of America (traditionally USA) (eng. The United States of America, USA) is a country which situated in North America. It ranks fourth in the world in terms of area (9,518,900 km²) and third in terms of its population (more than 300 million). The capital is the city of Washington. The United States is bordered by Canada to the north, Mexico to the south, and Russia Federation by sea. It is surrounded by the Pacific Ocean in the West and the Atlantic Ocean in the East. Administratively, the country consists of 50 states and the Federal District of Columbia. In addition, the United States also includes several islands. When the people of the United States are called Americans, they call their country by the common name America.

Results. The United States of America was founded in 1776 when thirty British colonies united and declared themselves independent. The struggle for independence will continue until 1783, and finally the colonialists will be defeated. The US Constitution was adopted in 1787 and the Bill of Rights in 1791. In 1860, a four-year civil war began between the country's south, where slavery remained, and the industrialized north. The victory of the Northern states in this civil war saved the country from disintegration and became the main factor in the abolition of slavery in the United States. After the First World War, there was a sharp turn in the US policy. That is, the USA has abandoned the policy of isolationism and has become an active participant in international relations. In 1945, the United States entered World War II as the world's most powerful nation, possessing its own nuclear weapons and continuing to oppose the Soviet Union until the late 1980s.

To date, the United States of America has the world's largest economy (\$14.2 trillion), the most powerful military force, including the largest navy, a permanent

seat in the UN Security Council, and the founding state of the North Atlantic Military Bloc (NATO) is considered The USA has the second largest nuclear arsenal in the world.

From the first days of the establishment of the American state, its leaders, politicians, scientific and cultural community, ordinary citizens imagined and recognized the United States of America as a country with a unique and special mission in the world. Thomas Jefferson described the United States as "the last hope of mankind" and "the adversary of ignorance and barbarism."

In the first articles of the Federalists in 1787, A. Hamilton wrote: "... today, the people of our country must answer a question that is very important to them: whether in the future the citizens, their community, will be able to create a good system of government based on their election, or whether they will be forever dependent and forced to claim their rights? If this statement is correct in some sense, then the period of crisis we are living in is temporary, if it is different and if we make a mistake in making a decision, it will be a disaster for the whole humanity.

In 1782, B. Franklin announced that the declaration of the United States of America and political independence was of great importance not only for "making people happy", but also for "improving the lives of people who are suffering from despotism in different parts of the world". Three years later, Adams puts forward an even more ambitious idea. That is, according to his definition: "Being the most powerful country in the world is written in the destiny of the USA." In other words, Americans see themselves as the chosen, superior nation. Accordingly, they are considered to be a model country for many countries of the world in terms of a special responsibility for protecting world peace and how to build social life and a legal state in the country.

If we observe the entire history of US foreign policy, the missionary idea has been dominant in it. However, America has manifested this global mission in different periods of history. At the same time, US history has been dominated by political ideas of isolationism, globalism, and pragmatism with varying degrees of success.

Traditionally, the United States has not sought to enter into alliances with other countries or to interfere in the political affairs of other countries. The main factors of this isolationism were the geographical situation of the country and, in turn, psychological factors. Geographically, North America was separated from the

European region by a vast ocean. At the same time, the lack of danger from Mexico and Canada and the acquisition of huge territories in the region for the United States caused him some feelings of satisfaction. These annexed territories were carried out without harming the interests of European countries.

Psychologically, the USA developed independently of Europe, which was full of social, political, religious and economic problems. The Americans were trying to build a new country that was different from the "superstition" countries of Europe and not liked the countries of the Old World. Isolationism, in turn, was also seen as the fruit of emerging and growing American supremacy.

At the same time, the active action of the United States in foreign policy is beginning to be seen, albeit slowly. For example, the Americans sent their naval squadron against the "barbarian" states that besieged US merchant ships, the 1812 war between the United States and Great Britain, the 1846 war with Mexico, which opposed the independence of Texas and its annexation to the United States, and the Spanish-American War that occurred in 1898 and the resulting acquisition of control of the Philippine Islands by the United States serves as clear evidence of this idea.

Conclusion. The policy of isolationism of the United States, which lasted for a century and a half, was replaced by the policy of globalism by the 20th century. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the activity of the United States in the field of international trade and commerce increased rapidly. America began to look for new trade markets, while at the same time, it began to establish its own naval bases abroad in order to protect its commercial interests and sea trade routes. The active involvement of the United States in international activities was accompanied by the strengthening of the idea of moralism. In May 1904, T.Roosevelt said: "If a nation conducts itself in the political and industrial spheres with dignity and decency, if it maintains order and acts according to its obligations, then there is no need for the United States to interfere in these public affairs. It is impudence or impotence that brings a civilized society to a crisis, and if such manifestations appear, it will eventually lead to the intervention of a civilized nation in this country, in which case the United States can act as a policeman in the Western Hemisphere, at least in the Caribbean. Fourteen years later, US President Woodrow Wilson, commenting on the US entry into the First World War, admitted that the US entered the war in an effort to ensure "democracy and peace in the world" and, as a result, "to put an end to all wars in the world". In its 14 points, it proposes

open diplomacy, self-government, independence of the seas, arms limitation, and the creation of a League of Nations that will unite the progressive countries of the world, which will serve to ensure collective peace.

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